

Realizing Network Analyzer Functionalities with an RF Signal Generator and Spectrum Analyzer: A Directional-Coupler-Free Approach

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Abstract

This work presents the implementation of a measurement system utilizing an RF signal generator and a spectrum analyzer to emulate key functionalities of a vector network analyzer (VNA). The approach eliminates the requirement of a directional coupler by using computational post-processing techniques. The proposed method provides a low-cost alternative for characterizing RF components and systems, suitable for laboratory-scale experiments and academic demonstrations. In this paper we show typically how we can use the Spectrum Analyzer to detect the amount of power/ current went back through reflection due to impedance mismatch.

1 Introduction

As demonstrated in [1], we needed to know how much power would have been reflected by various antennas we created for the RF evaporative cooling step. This approach eliminates the need of buying any directional coupler or Network Analyzer thus, cutting out the cost effectively. Motivation for a simplified approach using readily available instruments.

2 Methodology

2.1 System Setup

The experimental setup consisted of a Rohde & Schwarz RF Signal Generator (Model: **SMC100A**) and a Keysight Spectrum Analyzer (Model: **N9912C, FieldFox Series**). The signal generator provided a swept-frequency excitation signal, while the spectrum analyzer captured both the transmitted and reflected responses from the device under test (DUT). All instruments were connected using low-loss coaxial cables.

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2.2 Instrument Specifications

2.2.1 Keysight N9912C FieldFox Spectrum Analyzer

- **Frequency Range:** 5 kHz to 10 GHz
- **Dynamic Range:** > 100 dB
- **Resolution Bandwidths:** 1 Hz to 1 MHz
- **Display:** 6.5-inch
- **Battery Life:** Up to 4 hours
- **Weight:** Approximately 3.3 kg
- **Features:** Spectrum analysis, vector network analysis, cable and antenna testing, time-domain analysis

2.2.2 Rohde & Schwarz SMC100A Signal Generator (SG)

- **Frequency Range:** 9 kHz to 1.1 GHz or 3.2 GHz (depending on model)
- **Output Power:** Typ. > +17 dBm
- **Modulation:** AM, FM, PM, Pulse modulation
- **Phase Noise:** -111 dBc/Hz at 1 GHz, 20 kHz offset
- **Size:** Compact and lightweight design
- **Applications:** EMC testing, RF component characterization, educational purposes

2.3 Measurement Procedure

For measuring the power reflected back, we measured two different types of power:-

- The power that already went through our antenna and went all through the circuit.
- The power radiated by the antenna.

$$\boxed{\begin{aligned} \text{Power from SG} = & \text{Power Reflected to SG} \\ & + \text{To Spectrum Analyzer (SA)} + \text{Radiated by Antenna} \end{aligned}} \quad (1)$$

So, we deal with two types of circuits over here.

The circuits discussed here are so far simple and avoid any type of complexities, however we see encountered a lot of trouble while we tried to make the interface that can connect these two instruments from different companies and finally provide us with an interface that can help us to calibrate these two instruments together.

Later we extend this software and tried on different Signal Generator of other companies to ensure that the software works for a wide range of Spectrum Analyzers and Signal Generators.

As we see that the Analyzer is a mobile device, it is grounded by itself and we did not grounded the device separately. However the RF Signal Generator was grounded separately.

Figure 1: Circuit for observing how much power went through the antenna after emission and reflection back due to impedance mismatch.

Figure 2: Circuit used to analyze the shape of the power emitted by the antenna.

2.4 Software Implementation

The Spectrum Analyzer consisted of various markers which could be tuned manually; however, when we connected the Analyzer to our PC and attempted to control it using Python, we encountered several issues.

The first problem was that the Analyzer did not recognize the "Marker" or "Trace" as a programmable command. We were able to adjust the "Span" and the "Frequency Range Limits," but we were unable to move the "Marker." This posed a serious problem: if we could not position the marker correctly, we would not obtain the accurate power value at the resonance peak.

Subsequently, we attempted to identify which functions were recognized ("recognizable functions") and which were not ("non-recognizable functions") by the Analyzer. We began by predicting functions, sending commands, and trying various combinations, recording each syntax that the Analyzer accepted as valid input.

In essence, we experimented extensively with the instrument to discover a way to control the marker.

Every code we tested failed, except for the basic functions such as changing the frequency span. We even attempted to guess binary commands by sending them in multiple combinations, which also failed; the instrument did not recognize any of the guessed functions. Eventually, we decided not to move the peak. Instead, we observed that the RF Spectrum Analyzer includes a built-in function to detect peaks during frequency sweeps and store the data (using the max-hold option).

If we could access this function programmatically via Python, we would achieve our goal. After several trials, we succeeded in displaying the live spectrum data on the computer screen using Python.

We achieved live data analysis and forecasting on the PC. Subsequently, we printed the data (Power in dBm vs Frequency in MHz), and were able to store and export it in .csv format.

Later, we enhanced the software by enabling automatic detection of the VISA addresses of connected instruments, and identifying which device was the Spectrum Analyzer and which was the Signal Generator.

We also set the span of the RF Spectrum Analyzer according to the maximum and min-

imum values generated by the RF Signal Generator.

2.5 Resolution Problem

Once the software functioned correctly, we addressed the resolution issue. It was not possible for the Spectrum Analyzer to collect all frequencies precisely without discrepancies for an absolute step frequency. Therefore, we conducted multiple experiments to determine the optimal step frequency for different ranges of input frequencies, and configured it accordingly.

Sweep Span (MHz)	Step Frequency (MHz)
≥ 400	1.0
$200 \leq \text{Span} < 400$	0.5
< 200	Span/400

Table 1: Auto-selected Step Frequency Based on Sweep Span

The Dwell time gave the best value (Fastest and Precise) when we set it to 0.1s. Finally the software was ready and we were able to calibrate both of the instruments together.

3 Results

Now we will get two plots for two circuits.

- Power that went through the circuit. (refer fig:1)
- Power that was emitted by the antenna. (refer fig:2)

From these two data, we can plot a graph of how much power that went back due to impedance mismatch.

Figure 3: Graph plotted by the software depicting the amount of power that went through the circuit.

Figure 4: Graph plotted by the software depicting the amount of power that got emitted.

Figure 5: Circuit depicting the setup. (refer fig: 2)

Here is the Graphical User Interface version of the software.
 Later we added a graph which will be plotted immediately but in milli-Watt just below Graph showing the power in (dBm)

Figure 6: Enter Caption

4 Conclusion

This software accurately measures both powers, allowing us to determine the power reflected back from the antenna due to impedance mismatch.

An important point to note is that the .csv file is stored only after the entire reading is completed, rather than value by value, thereby enhancing performance. Moreover, if the device is stopped midway without properly ending the sweep, the data are still stored up to the point where the sweep was completed, thus providing additional benefits.

5 Python Code

```
1 import sys
2 import threading
3 import time
4 import numpy as np
5 import pyvisa
6 import csv
7 from PyQt6.QtWidgets import (
8     QApplication, QWidget, QPushButton, QVBoxLayout, QLabel,
9     QLineEdit, QFileDialog, QMessageBox
10 )
11 from PyQt6.QtCore import pyqtSignal, QObject
12 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
13 from matplotlib.backends.backend_qtagg import FigureCanvasQTAgg as
14     FigureCanvas
15 from pathlib import Path
16
17 class Communicate(QObject):
18     data_signal = pyqtSignal(np.ndarray, np.ndarray)
19     finished_signal = pyqtSignal()
20
21 class LivePlotCanvas(FigureCanvas):
22     def __init__(self):
23         self.fig, self.ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(8, 4))
24         super().__init__(self.fig)
25         self.ax.set_title("Live RF Spectrum (dBm)")
26         self.ax.set_xlabel("Frequency (MHz)")
27         self.ax.set_ylabel("Power (dBm)")
28         self.line, = self.ax.plot([], [], 'b-')
29         self.ax.grid(True)
30         self.fig.tight_layout()
31
32     def update_plot(self, freqs, powers):
33         self.line.set_data(freqs / 1e6, powers)
34         self.ax.relim()
35         self.ax.autoscale_view()
36         self.draw()
37
38 class LivePlotCanvasMW(FigureCanvas):
39     def __init__(self):
40         self.fig, self.ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(8, 3))
41         super().__init__(self.fig)
42         self.ax.set_title("Power in milliWatts")
43         self.ax.set_xlabel("Frequency (MHz)")
44         self.ax.set_ylabel("Power (mW)")
45         self.line, = self.ax.plot([], [], 'g-')
46         self.ax.grid(True)
47         self.fig.tight_layout()
48
49     def update_plot(self, freqs, powers_mw):
50         self.line.set_data(freqs / 1e6, powers_mw)
51         self.ax.relim()
52         self.ax.autoscale_view()
53         self.draw()
54
```

```

55
56
57 class MachineApp(QWidget):
58     """Main GUI application"""
59
60     def __init__(self):
61         super().__init__()
62         self.setWindowTitle("Live RF Sweep and Analyzer")
63
64         # --- Signals --- #
65         self.comm = Communicate()
66         self.comm.data_signal.connect(self.update_plot)
67         self.comm.finished_signal.connect(self.on_finished)
68
69         # --- User inputs --- #
70         self.start_freq_input = QLineEdit("600e6")
71         self.stop_freq_input = QLineEdit("1000e6")
72         self.step_freq_input = QLineEdit("1e6")
73         self.power_input = QLineEdit("0")
74         self.dwell_input = QLineEdit("0.1")
75
76         self.center_freq_input = QLineEdit()
77         self.span_input = QLineEdit()
78
79         # Auto populate centre & span for the initial defaults
80         self.update_center_span_step()
81
82         # Connect edits so any change in start/stop automatically
83         # refreshes
84         self.start_freq_input.editingFinished.connect(self.
85             update_center_span_step)
86         self.stop_freq_input.editingFinished.connect(self.
87             update_center_span_step)
88
89         # Allow user to override by clicking the fields      nothing
90         # special is
91         # required: once the user types, the edited value stays until
92         # they edit
93         # start/stop again.
94
95         # --- Buttons --- #
96         self.start_button = QPushButton("Start Live Sweep")
97         self.start_button.clicked.connect(self.start_measurement)
98         self.stop_button = QPushButton("Stop")
99         self.stop_button.clicked.connect(self.stop_measurement)
100        self.stop_button.setEnabled(False)
101
102        # --- Layout --- #
103        layout = QVBoxLayout()
104        layout.addWidget(QLabel("Signal Generator Settings"))
105        layout.addWidget(QLabel("Start Frequency (Hz):"))
106        layout.addWidget(self.start_freq_input)
107        layout.addWidget(QLabel("Stop Frequency (Hz):"))
108        layout.addWidget(self.stop_freq_input)
109        layout.addWidget(QLabel("Step Frequency (Hz):"))
110        layout.addWidget(self.step_freq_input)
111        layout.addWidget(QLabel("Power (dBm):"))
112        layout.addWidget(self.power_input)

```

```

108     layout.addWidget(QLabel("Dwell Time (sec):"))
109     layout.addWidget(self.dwell_input)
110
111     layout.addWidget(QLabel("RF Spectrum Analyzer Settings"))
112     layout.addWidget(QLabel("Center Frequency (Hz):"))
113     layout.addWidget(self.center_freq_input)
114     layout.addWidget(QLabel("Span (Hz):"))
115     layout.addWidget(self.span_input)
116
117     layout.addWidget(self.start_button)
118     layout.addWidget(self.stop_button)
119
120     self.plot_canvas = LivePlotCanvas()
121     layout.addWidget(self.plot_canvas)
122
123     self.plot_canvas_mw = LivePlotCanvasMW()
124     layout.addWidget(self.plot_canvas_mw)
125
126     self.setLayout(layout)
127
128     # --- Runtime vars --- #
129     self._running = False
130     self.rf_freqs = None
131     self.csv_path = None
132
133     # Keyword lists for auto detection
134     self.signal_gen_keywords = [
135         "SMC", "SMA", "SMB", "SGS", "SMU",
136         "E8247", "E8257", "MXG", "EXG",
137         "MG369", "SSG5000", "Siglent", "PSG", "AWG"
138     ]
139
140     self.spectrum_analyzer_keywords = [
141         "FieldFox", "PSA", "ESA", "SSA3000", "XSA1000",
142         "Signal Hound", "Spike", "Keysight", "Agilent"
143     ]
144
145     #
146     -----
147
148     # Helper methods for automatic centre/span & step size
149     #
150     -----
151
152     def update_center_span_step(self):
153         """Compute centre, span and an appropriate default step size.
154         """
155         try:
156             start_freq = float(eval(self.start_freq_input.text()))
157             stop_freq = float(eval(self.stop_freq_input.text()))
158         except Exception:
159             return # silently ignore until valid numbers are entered
160
161         span = abs(stop_freq - start_freq)
162         center = (start_freq + stop_freq) / 2.0

```

```

160     # Populate the fields      these can still be edited manually
161         later
162     self.center_freq_input.setText(f"{center}")
163     self.span_input.setText(f"{span}")
164
165     # Choose step resolution based on the span (examples provided
166         by user)
167     if span >= 400e6:
168         default_step = 1e6 # 1 MHz for 400MHz span
169     elif span >= 200e6:
170         default_step = 0.5e6 # 0.5 MHz for 200MHz span
171     else:
172         # Fallback: aim for ~400 points across the sweep
173         default_step = span / 400 if span else 1e6
174
175     self.step_freq_input.setText(f"{default_step}")
176
177     # -----
178
179     # Instrument handling & measurement logic      unchanged except for
180         using
181     # the a u t o populated centre/span/step
182     # -----
183
184     def detect_and_select_devices(self):
185         self.rm = pyvisa.ResourceManager()
186         resources = self.rm.list_resources()
187         sig_gen_address = None
188         rf_analyzer_address = None
189
190         for addr in resources:
191             try:
192                 inst = self.rm.open_resource(addr)
193                 idn = inst.query("*IDN?").strip()
194                 inst.close()
195                 print(f"Detected {addr}: {idn}")
196
197                 if any(keyword in idn for keyword in self.
198                     signal_gen_keywords):
199                     sig_gen_address = addr
200                 elif any(keyword in idn for keyword in self.
201                     spectrum_analyzer_keywords):
202                     rf_analyzer_address = addr
203
204             except Exception as e:
205                 print(f"Could not identify {addr}: {e}")
206
207         if not sig_gen_address or not rf_analyzer_address:
208             QMessageBox.critical(
209                 self,
210                 "Detection Failed",
211                 "Could not auto-detect both Signal Generator and RF
212                     Analyzer.\nPlease ensure they are connected and
213                     powered on."
214             )

```

```

207         return None, None
208
209     return sig_gen_address, rf_analyzer_address
210
211     def start_measurement(self):
212         try:
213             # R e compute centre/span in case user changed start/stop
214             # and did not leave the field
215             self.update_center_span_step()
216
217             self.start_freq = float(eval(self.start_freq_input.text()))
218             self.stop_freq = float(eval(self.stop_freq_input.text()))
219             self.step_freq = float(eval(self.step_freq_input.text()))
220             self.power_dbm = float(eval(self.power_input.text()))
221             self.dwell_time = float(eval(self.dwell_input.text()))
222             self.center_freq = float(eval(self.center_freq_input.text(
223             )))
224             self.span = float(eval(self.span_input.text()))
225         except Exception as e:
226             QMessageBox.critical(self, "Input Error", f"Invalid input:
227             {e}")
228             return
229
230         desktop = Path.home() / "Desktop"
231         default_file = desktop / "rf_live_data.csv"
232         path, _ = QFileDialog.getSaveFileName(
233             self,
234             "Save CSV File",
235             str(default_file), # now opens on Desktop
236             "CSV Files (*.csv)"
237         )
238         if not path:
239             return
240         self.csv_path = path
241
242         self._running = True
243         self.start_button.setEnabled(False)
244         self.stop_button.setEnabled(True)
245
246         sig_address, rf_address = self.detect_and_select_devices()
247         if not sig_address or not rf_address:
248             self.start_button.setEnabled(True)
249             self.stop_button.setEnabled(False)
250             self._running = False
251             return
252
253         try:
254             self.sig_gen = self.rm.open_resource(sig_address)
255             self.rf_inst = self.rm.open_resource(rf_address)
256         except Exception as e:
257             QMessageBox.critical(self, "Connection Error", f"Failed to
258             connect instruments: {e}")
259             self.start_button.setEnabled(True)
260             self.stop_button.setEnabled(False)
261             self._running = False
262             return
263
264         self.sig_gen.write(f"POW {self.power_dbm}DBM")

```

```

261     self.sig_gen.write("OUTP ON")
262
263     self.rf_inst.write(f":FREQ:CENT {self.center_freq}Hz")
264     self.rf_inst.write(f":FREQ:SPAN {self.span}Hz")
265     self.rf_inst.write(":BAND:RES 1MHz")
266     self.rf_inst.write(":SWE:POIN 401")
267     self.rf_inst.write(":TRAC1:TYPE MAXH")
268     self.rf_inst.write(":INIT:CONT ON")
269
270     start_rf = float(self.rf_inst.query(":FREQ:STAR?"))
271     stop_rf = float(self.rf_inst.query(":FREQ:STOP?"))
272     self.rf_freqs = np.linspace(start_rf, stop_rf, 401)
273
274     self.last_powers = None
275
276     self.sweep_thread = threading.Thread(target=self.
277         signal_generator_sweep)
278     self.rf_poll_thread = threading.Thread(target=self.
279         rf_polling_loop)
280
281     self.sweep_thread.start()
282     self.rf_poll_thread.start()
283
284     def signal_generator_sweep(self):
285         for freq in np.arange(self.start_freq, self.stop_freq + self.
286             step_freq, self.step_freq):
287             if not self._running:
288                 break
289             self.sig_gen.write(f"FREQ {freq}HZ")
290             time.sleep(self.dwell_time)
291
292     self.sig_gen.write("OUTP OFF")
293     self._running = False
294
295     def rf_polling_loop(self):
296         while self._running:
297             try:
298                 powers = self.rf_inst.query_ascii_values(":TRAC:DATA?")
299                 if len(powers) == len(self.rf_freqs):
300                     self.last_powers = powers
301                     self.comm.data_signal.emit(self.rf_freqs, np.array(
302                         powers))
303             except Exception as e:
304                 print("Error polling RF data:", e)
305                 time.sleep(0.5)
306
307     if self.csv_path and self.last_powers is not None:
308         with open(self.csv_path, mode='w', newline='') as file:
309             writer = csv.writer(file)
310             writer.writerow(["Frequency (MHz)", "Power (dBm)", "
311                 Power (mW)"])
312             for f, p in zip(self.rf_freqs, self.last_powers):
313                 writer.writerow([f / 1e6, p, 10 ** (p / 10)])
314
315     try:
316         self.sig_gen.close()
317         self.rf_inst.close()
318         self.rm.close()

```

```

314         except: # noqa: E722         ignore any errors while closing
315             pass
316
317         self.comm.finished_signal.emit()
318
319     def update_plot(self, freqs, powers):
320         self.plot_canvas.update_plot(freqs, powers)
321         powers_mw = 10 ** (np.array(powers) / 10)
322         self.plot_canvas_mw.update_plot(freqs, powers_mw)
323
324     def on_finished(self):
325         self.start_button.setEnabled(True)
326         self.stop_button.setEnabled(False)
327         QMessageBox.information(self, "Done", f"Measurement complete.\n
nData saved to:\n{self.csv_path}")
328
329     def stop_measurement(self):
330         self._running = False
331
332
333 if __name__ == "__main__":
334     app = QApplication(sys.argv)
335     window = MachineApp()
336     window.show()
337     sys.exit(app.exec())

```

6 Acknowledgment

I would like to sincerely thank Professor Lev Khaykovich, Head of the Ultracold Atoms Laboratory, for granting me the opportunity to contribute to this project and for his guidance and support during the experimental activities conducted in his laboratory.[1]

References

- [1] R. Das and L. Khaykovich, *Design and Characterization of Essential Components for a Magneto-Optical Trap*, Zenodo, 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16758110.